

Transcriber effects in the Icelandic parliament corpus^{*}

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Abstract

The Icelandic parliament corpus is being used to study individual lifespan change in sociolinguistic style-shift. We report on how the word order effect in question is affected by decisions made by those who transcribe the speeches and show that while some changes are made by the transcribers, the overall pattern of linguistic usage is not substantially altered. Ideally, each recording is manually checked by an annotator, but automatic annotation can be used with the understanding that quantitative findings are subject to minor errors.

Keywords

sociolinguistics, style-shift, Icelandic, error analysis, transcription, parliament speeches

1. Introduction

In the ERC-funded project Explaining Individual Lifespan Change (EILisCh), a key goal is to investigate how individual Members of Parliament change their linguistic behavior with respect to sociolinguistic style-shift over time. Sociolinguistic style-shift is the way in which speakers alter the rate at which they use variable linguistic phenomena depending on the context in which the speaking takes place. For example, some variants are used more frequently in formal speech and other more frequently in informal speech. Using the Icelandic Parliament Corpus (Steingrímsson, Barkarson, and Örnólfsson 2020) and automatic extraction of relevant examples, this kind of an analysis can be carried out very rapidly. However, in order to verify that the automatic methods are justified, it is necessary to evaluate how their quality compares with manually checking the data. This study adds that crucial step.

2. Stylistic Fronting in Icelandic Parliament Corpus

As in other language variation and change studies, this project focuses on certain grammatical variables. The variables monitored in the study are all stylistic indicators, with Stylistic Fronting (SF) as the study's primary variable. Stylistic Fronting is an optional movement in Icelandic of a

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syntactic head (/word) or a phrase to the front of a clause that has a phonological subject gap (Maling 1980; Thráinsson 2007; Holmberg 2006). An example of SF is given in (1) where the non-finite verb *lesnar* 'read' is moved in front of the finite auxiliary *eru* 'are' in a relative clause where the grammatical subject has been extracted. Example (2) represents a parallel sentence in which SF has not been applied.

- (1) Bækur [_{CP} sem lesnar eru til skemmtunar] eru bestar.
 books [_{CP} that read are for entertainment] are best
 'Books that are read for entertainment are the best ones.'
- (2) Bækur [_{CP} sem eru lesnar til skemmtunar] eru bestar.
 books [_{CP} that are read for entertainment] are best
 'Books that are read for entertainment are the best ones.'

SF has no effect on truth-conditional meaning, and its only clear meaning component is a sociolinguistic one; the movement is associated with formal style. SF is found in both main clauses and subordinate clauses, as long as the subject is not phonologically overt. To control for factors that can condition the use of SF¹ we limit the scope of the study to the following word orders involving the complementizer *sem* that introduces Icelandic relative clauses (e.g., by excluding elements other than non-finite main verbs).

We choose SF as a phenomenon to be studied because the rate of SF is a good indicator of the level of formality with a sample of speech data and therefore it is a good variable to study style shift. It is also convenient to use because it can be relatively reliably extracted with automatic methods, although this paper is an inquiry into just how reliably such automatic methods are. The choice of the parliament corpus as opposed to other corpora stems from the fact that by using speeches given from the same spot and social context, we can control for other contextual factors, and we have found in our previous research that fluctuations in the use of SF in parliament speeches reflect in an interesting way what is going on in the professional lives of the parliament members. Although we currently limit the scope of our inquiry in this way, our findings will provide a useful point of comparison when studying SF in other corpora in future work.

3. Transcriber error analysis

In order to estimate the effect of transcriber error, i.e. differences between what the Member of Parliament said and what was transcribed by the employees of the parliament, we manually checked all the examples of Stylistic Fronting in our study of MP Ásmundur Einar Daðason (Stefánsdóttir and Ingason 2024). In terms of sampling, we included all speeches given by this MP during the period in question and all relative clauses of the type described above. Each relevant token was first automatically annotated as 1 for Stylistic Fronting and 0 for an absence of Stylistic Fronting where it could have applied. Then the examples were all manually annotated as well so that we could check whether SF was correctly annotated by the automatic

¹Wood's (2011) study showed that there are some prosodic factors that affect the use of SF, such as the constituent's number of syllables, building on earlier work that suggests that optionality in Icelandic syntax may be sensitive to favoring a regular trochaic stress pattern (Ingason 2008).

process or if the transcriber had reversed the word order, i.e. inserted Stylistic Fronting where there was none or removed Stylistic Fronting that was present in the speech. We excluded tokens that were unresolved because the recording was missing from the parliament website. The transcribers in this case are the employees of the parliament who transcribe the speeches based on audio and video recordings from parliament sessions. All speeches delivered in the Icelandic Parliament are documented and published in open access on the parliament's website. The transcribing process is relatively simple and relies mainly on recordings from a recording room above the parliamentary chamber. The transcribers' general procedure is to transcribe verbatim after the recordings, except in cases of obvious grammatical errors and unfinished utterances (Skrifstofa Alþingis 2017). The following is one example of an utterance that had to be corrected by our annotators:

- (3) fjármagnið sem er verið að veita í landsbyggðarháskólana fjóra
funds that are being to allocated in countryside universities four
'... funds that are being allocated to the four countryside universities ...'

This transcription from the parliament had to be corrected because the MP did in fact say *verið er* 'being are' with a Stylistic Fronting word order.

We found that the rate of Stylistic Fronting was 73.3% (770/1050) in the automatic annotation that was directly based on the transcript and the rate was 72.9% (642/881) in the data that had been manually corrected against the recordings. This means that we looked at 1050 data points and after excluding examples that are not potential cases of Stylistic Fronting, we had 881 one examples left to carry out the analysis. We found 75 examples where an apparent Stylistic Fronting instance in the transcription had been introduced by the transcriber and 23 examples where there was no Stylistic Fronting in the transcript, but the MP had in fact uttered one as evidenced by listening to the recording. We find that this difference is not significant (X-squared = 0.031105, df = 1, p-value = 0.86).

As we are interested in studying changes in the rate of Stylistic Fronting over time for individual MP's, we furthermore plot the uncorrected and corrected rates for Ásmundur Einar Daðason throughout his political career as shown in Figure 1. It is obvious from the graph that the main trends found in the uncorrected data are replicated in the corrected data. As discussed by Stefánsdóttir and Ingason (2024), the lower rate of SF in 2013–14 and again in 2016 correlates with periods during which Daðason was going through crises in his career. He changed parties in 2011, became very unpopular and there were calls for his resignation, following which he lowered his use of SF in 2013–14. In 2015 he was reported to have been intoxicated and vomited on another passenger on an airplane, after which he lowered his use of SF in 2016. We hypothesize that the lower rate of SF during these periods corresponds to laying low and becoming more informal as a reactive response to a crisis. The wiggles in the data are almost identical in the corrected and uncorrected data.

Figure 1: Error analysis in transcription by year

4. Conclusion

The fact that the rate of Stylistic Fronting is very similar in the automatically extracted findings and the manually checked ones is reassuring and suggests that in cases where resources are not available to check every token, it is valid to use the automatic analysis as a proxy for what a more detailed study would find. However, the automatic annotation does not match the manually checked one exactly, and therefore it is also the case that manual checking is valuable and preferable whenever this is a feasible option.

This means that for future research, one can remain optimistic that automatic methods can speed up the process of big data humanities approaches to studies of parliament speeches. However, any given project that focuses on a new variable must verify the accuracy of the automatic coding that is extracted based on Natural Language Processing and we must stress that our finding that the rate of Stylistic Fronting can be reliably extracted does not extend to other objects of study without further verification.

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